

Submission date: October 25, 2022

Policy Sponsor: Orbital Exploration Technologies, Inc.

Author: Mr. Dexter Pormento Bano Jr.

Receiving Bodies:

1. Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP)
2. House of Representatives, Philippines
3. Senate of the Philippines

NEW POLICY PROPOSAL
for the
INCLUSION OF COMMERCIAL SPACE TRANSPORTATION AND
SPACE LAUNCH SERVICE PROVIDERS REGULATION IN THE
PHILIPPINE CIVIL AIR REGULATIONS (PCAR), FORMATION OF A
NATIONAL ASSEMBLY FOR SPACECRAFT AND LAUNCHER
ACCREDITATION (NASLA), AND THE ESTABLISHMENT OF
PHILIPPINE SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE FOR AEROSPACE
DEVELOPMENT (PHILSEZAD)

I. Background/Reason for Proposed Policy

The Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP) is the agency responsible for “implementing policies on civil aviation to ensure safe, economical, and efficient air travel.” Currently, the existing policies are only suitable for aircrafts and other related works and this proposal aims to provide a framework based on the needs and perspective of a new player in the global aerospace industry. This document focuses on giving an initial pathway for the future of commercial spaceflight industry in the Philippines.

The Policy Sponsor seeks for its own regulation through this proposal in order to become a use case for future policy construction within the land. The basis of this proposal is the Code of Federal Regulations Title 14: Aeronautics and Space; Chapter III: Commercial Space Transportation, Federal Aviation Administration, Department of Transportation.

II. The Proposed Policy

ARTICLE I

GENERAL PROVISIONS

SECTION 1. *Title.* – This policy and its rules shall be known and cited as the “Spacecraft and Launch Vehicle Development and Regulation Policy.”

SECTION 2. *Declaration of Policies.* – It is to be declared by the State that all space launch service providers and all forms of unmanned spacecrafts being (a) designed, (b) developed, (c) manufactured, and (d) scheduled for launch and/or tests, shall be registered under the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP). Such efforts shall be sufficient in order to ensure air and environmental safety and

overall national security of the constituents residing, arriving, and leaving in the territories of the Republic of the Philippines.

The best interests of the citizens of the State shall be of supreme importance in the enactment of this proposed policy. It shall be in accordance to the “Strategic Trade Management Act” of the Philippines also known as Republic Act No. 10697; the “Philippine Space Act” otherwise known as Republic Act No. 11363; and the “United Nations Treaties and Principles on Outer Space”.

Toward this end, the State shall:

- a. Secure the safety of the citizens in the aspects of air, land, water, and environment through the basis of existing laws of the land;
- b. Ensure that all developers, designers, and manufacturers of spacecrafts and space launch service related products shall be registered, filed, and informed to the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP);
- c. Prevent irresponsible tests and launches that may affect the welfare of many;
- d. Perform technical due diligence before allowing any tests and launches;
- e. Schedule tests and launches after going through required technical due diligence in order to closely monitor developments and to provide additional layer of safety;
- f. Conduct public and private educational campaigns to properly disseminate information;
- g. Protect the welfare of other living creatures in land, water, and air; and
- h. Encourage cooperation between different stakeholders such as but not limited to the industry, the government and the academe.

No company, organization, group or individual shall be allowed to conduct any form of tests without complying to the declared requirements of the State. The company, organization, group or individual must also adhere to the Strategic Trade Management Act of the Philippines and must be duly authorized and certified by the Strategy Trade Management Office of the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI-STMO).

It is hereby recognized that the administrative processes for the cases of legally compliant entities are the most expeditious to avoid delays in any research and development procedures and other necessary compliances.

SECTION 3. Objectives. – The policy, through this proposal, shall provide a framework to allow simpler compliance procedures to spacecraft and space launch service developers, designers, manufacturers, and providers of any kind in the State. Pursuant to this, it shall create an independent National Assembly for Spacecraft and Launcher Accreditation (NASLA), which the board shall be composed of three (3) representatives from the industry, three (3) representatives from the government, and three (3) representatives from the research and academic sectors. NASLA will exercise the functions related to the accreditation, guidance, acceleration, and other related recommendations of new participants in the spacecraft and space launcher development industry in the State.

The creation of a Special Economic Zone in accordance to the guidelines set by Republic Act No. 7916 or “The Special Economic Zone Act of 1995” will be called Philippine Special Economic Zone for Aerospace Development (PhilSEZAD). PhilSEZAD will be an ECOZONE intended for the development of aeronautical and aerospace related activities which include spacecraft and launch vehicle development. The said ECOZONE will be composed of industrial estates such as launch pads, assembly facilities, and test centers, financial centers, export and import processing zones, free trade zones, and research and development centers.

SECTION 4. Definition of Terms. – For the purpose of this policy proposal, the following terms are defined:

- a. *Academe* refers to educational institutions that offers engineering programs focusing on safety, machine design, aeronautics, aerospace, astronautics, electronics, and research and development in general;
- b. *Casualty* refers to injuries, fatalities or death;
- c. *Contingency Abort* refers to the termination of vehicle flight due to any potential hazard during ascent or descent, that involves and concerns public safety and safety of any property based on the approved mission rules and procedures. Contingency abort includes redirected landings at a predetermined alternative location, land or water, as approved prior to conducting the mission;
- d. *Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP)* refers to a multi-role Philippine government agency that regulates aviation, air traffic management, and air safety;
- e. *ECOZONE* refers to a special economic zone (SEZ) that are selected areas either highly developed or scheduled to be developed for specific economic activity purposes;
- f. *Emergency Abort* refers to the ceasing of vehicle flight to minimize the risk of public and property hazard. Emergency abort includes vehicle failures and safety-critical systems to an extent that contingency abort is not possible;
- g. *Flight Summary* refers to the report documenting the result of a launch or a flight;
- h. *Launch Safety System* refers to a control, operational procedure, a software, a hardware, a process, or an item that can be triggered or executed to exercise safety;
- i. *Government* refers to the governing body of the State;
- j. *Industry* refers to for profit organizations and participants that develop spacecrafts and launcher vehicles;
- k. *Launch* refers to putting a spacecraft or launch vehicle from earth in a certain trajectory towards outer space which involves pre- and post- launch operations;
- l. *Launch Accident* refers to any launch and flight related fatalities and damages including injuries, death, destruction of properties that is not associated with the flight or the intended launch site or destination area;
- m. *Launch Pad* refers to an area identified for launching and testing launch vehicles and other forms of space craft that usually has a platform and a supporting structure;
- n. *Launch Vehicle* refers to an engineered rocket carrier that can carry a specific payload or spacecraft;
- o. *Monthly Development Summary Report* refers to a document that contains the monthly progress report of any spacecraft and launch vehicle development;
- p. *National Assembly for Spacecraft and Launcher Accreditation (NASLA)* refers to independent group that will exercise the functions related to the accreditation, guidance, acceleration, and other related recommendations of new participants in the spacecraft and space launcher development industry in the State;
- q. *Permit* refers to the authorization by the CAAP to perform test flights and launches including reentries;
- r. *Philippine Special Economic Zone for Aerospace Development (PhilSEZAD)* refers to a special economic zone intended for the conduct of any aeronautical and astronautical projects developments/activities;
- s. *Post-launch Operations* refers to the concluding procedures after any flight or launch which includes the deployment of any payload or spacecraft, final vehicle control exercises, reaching the right apogee, and submission of Flight Summary to CAAP;
- t. *Populated Area* refers to a location occupied by any group of living human beings located in any geographical location, inside or outside a structure, land or water;
- u. *Pre-launch Operations* refers to the preliminary procedures leading to launch which includes securing a permit that has a flight schedule and time approximation, detailed critical steps in conducting flight, safety measures including Contingency Abort and Emergency Abort plans, and a lost potential hazards;
- v. *Registrant* refers to any individual, group, school, college, university, organization or company;
- w. *Safety* refers to the overall well-being of the public, the properties, and the environment;

- x. *Spacecraft* refers to a machine or vehicle engineered, designed, and manufactured to fly to outer space which includes satellites and other payloads;
- y. *United Nations Treaties and Principles on Outer Space* refers to text of treaties and principles governing the activities of States in the exploration and use of outer space, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly;

ARTICLE II

NATIONAL ASSEMBLY FOR SPACECRAFT AND LAUNCHER ACCREDITATION

SECTION 5. *National Assembly for Spacecraft and Launcher Accreditation (NASLA)*. – This independent entity will be organized and attached to the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP). The duty of NASLA will be the following:

- a. Ensure the safety of the public and the environment at all times by issuing guidelines and permits to launch service providers located in the country;
- b. Update the rules and regulations related to the accreditation and registration of all types of spacecraft, payloads, and launch vehicles;
- c. Governance of the Philippine Special Economic Zone for Aerospace Development;
- d. Collaborate with other government agencies like the Philippine Space Agency (PhilSA), Department of Trade and Industry – Strategic Trade Management Office (DTI-STMO), Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP), Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG), Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), and Department of National Defense (DND) to formulate comprehensive safety measures and guidelines for tests and flights;
- e. Formulate cohesive trainings and seminars for industry players and for the general public;
- f. Act as a policy-making body;
- g. Register all spacecrafts, launch vehicles, and other payloads; and
- h. Monitor all tests and flights.

SECTION 6. *Composition of the NASLA*. The NASLA shall be composed of a Board and a Chairman.

The Board shall be composed of three (3) representatives from the industry, one (1) representative from the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP), one (1) representative from the Philippine Space Agency (PhilSA), one (1) representative from the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), and three representatives from the academic and research sector.

The members of the Board shall receive a reasonable per diem allowance for each meeting attended.

The Board, aside from making policies will also serve as the Appeals Committee for contested concerns and petitions by any stakeholder or concerned group or individual.

The Chairman shall implement and execute policies pursuant to the provisions of this policy.

The NASLA may hire various experts and professionals locally or abroad that can serve as consultants. These experts and professionals must have a proven set of expertise and track record in their respective fields. These members shall receive a reasonable honorarium for each meeting attended.

The Board shall elect a Deputy Chairman for Administration whom will be in-charge of human resource development, property and logistics management, and other administrative functions.

The Board shall elect a Deputy Chairman for Registry whom will be in-charge of the registration of local spacecraft and launch service developer, designer, manufacturer, and provider.

The Board shall elect a Deputy Chairman for Treasury whom will be in-charge of assets and financial management.

The Board shall elect a Deputy Chairman for Research and Development whom will be in-charge of carrying out activities aimed at innovation, coordinating research, and guaranteeing the quality of projects, products, and services in order to maintain global competitiveness.

The Board shall elect a Spokesperson whom will be in-charge of communicating information to the public and to other stakeholders.

ARTICLE III

SPACECRAFT AND LAUNCH VEHICLE REGISTRATION

A. APPLICATION TO GOVERNMENT AGENCIES FOR THE DECLARATION OF LEGALLY INTENDED DEVELOPMENT

SECTION 7. *Certificate Declaring a Registration of Spacecraft and Launch Vehicle.* – A Certificate Declaring the registration of a spacecraft or launch vehicle is issued to individuals, groups, organizations, schools, universities, colleges or companies. The Certificate must clearly state that the development is voluntary and not sponsored by the State and is pursuant to Republic Act 11363 and Republic Act 10697. The Certificate must be issued during the design or prototyping phase.

SECTION 8. *Duty of the NASLA, CAAP, PhilSA, DND, DTI, DILG or DENR.* – It shall be the duty of NASLA, CAAP, PhilSA, DND, DTI, DILG or DENR, which has specific fiduciary duties to exert all efforts covered by their mandate to maintain the integrity of the spacecraft and launch vehicle industry by issuing permits after conducting due diligence to each registrant.

SECTION 9. *Procedures for registration of launch vehicles and all types of spacecraft.* – If an individual, group, organization, academia or company intends to design, manufacture, and launch spacecraft or launch vehicle in the territory of the Republic of the Philippines, the following guidelines should be considered:

- a. Any spacecraft or launch vehicle weighing at least 0.025 kilogram (kg.) or 0.0551 pound (lbs.), and has a height of at least 0.05 meter (m.) or 0.16 foot (ft.) shall be endorsed to NASLA with the following documents:
 - Blueprint of the spacecraft or launch vehicle;
 - authorization and certification from the Department of Trade and Industry – Strategic Trade Management Office (DTI-STMO);
 - test and launch parameters and objectives;
 - Comprehensive list of suppliers which must contain their company name, address, contact details, and point person;
 - Gantt chart of scheduled activities; and
 - Safety Manual that contains the Launch Safety System;
- b. NASLA shall go through the documents and provide a comprehensive feedback within the next thirty (30) working days;
- c. Once NASLA clears the development of the submitted spacecraft or launch vehicle, the project shall be forwarded to the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) and the

corresponding Local Government Unit (LGU) where the development is taking place within the next five (5) working days;

- d. NASLA must forward the endorsement to PhilSA and CAAP for the approval of scheduled flight and launch activities (if there is any) within the airspace of the territory of the Republic of the Philippines; and
- e. Individuals, groups, organizations, academia, and companies shall provide a Monthly Development Summary Report to NASLA every 20th day of the month for close monitoring of the development. This shall include both the successful tests and failed tests.

ARTICLE IV

COMMON PROCEDURE

SECTION 10. *Procedure if permits cannot be obtained.* – Proof of efforts including letters, letter attachments, electronic mails, electronic mail attachments, and letter of intent/appeal must be submitted to the main office of NASLA in case the permits cannot be obtained or application has been declined.

SECTION 11. *Petition for Reconsideration.* – A Petition for Reconsideration shall be prepared by the developer/s of the spacecraft or launch vehicle concerned. An assistance from a legal counsel can be necessary and may be retained.

The said petition shall contain the documents mention in Article IV Section 10 and shall state the facts necessary to establish the merits of the case. The petitioners/applicants/developers must be at least eighteen (18) years of age, in possession of full civil capacity and legal rights; of good moral character; and have not been convicted in any type of crime of any type.

The petition should be submitted to any NASLA office within sixty (60) days after the date of receipt of the letter of rejection from NASLA. Failure to do so would mean that parties/applicants/petitioners/developers will be required to start all over again.

SECTION 12. *Publication.* – Upon receipt by the NASLA of the petition and its supporting documents, a copy of the petition shall be published once a week for four (4) successive Mondays in a newspaper of general circulation.

SECTION 13. *Objection to the Petition.* – These are subjects to rejection of petition and/or application;

- a. Any lack of foundational expertise and/or knowledge in developing a spacecraft or launch vehicle would result to a denial of the petition;
- b. Projects that are perceived to do structural failure within a population and can cause other forms of damages and casualties;
- c. Teams who have at least fifty-one (51) percent of their members classified as minors or below the age of eighteen (18);
- d. Teams who have not identified a clear project plan, intent of development, and security measures/protocols;
- e. At least one (1) team member has been convicted in any type of crime within or outside the Republic of the Philippines; and
- f. At least one (1) team member has been involved in money laundering or violation of R.A. 10697.

SECTION 14. *Repository of Orders and Registry of NASLA (NASLA - RepOR).* – The NASLA shall create a publicly-available and fully-updated database showing the issuance of cases, orders, registrations, and other types of publications. This database shall be governed by the provisions of Republic Act 10173,

otherwise known as the “Data Privacy Act of 2012” and the provisions of Executive Order No. 02 series of 2016 or the “Executive Order on Freedom of Information (FOI).”

SECTION 15. *Assistance to Academia and Start-Up Businesses.* – These are the following assistance available for start-up businesses with less than five (5) years of operation and research teams from schools and universities:

- a. Start-up businesses can avail grants and subsidies, venture capital, and expedited processing of applications under the provisions of Republic Act 11337 also known as “Innovative Startup Act”; and
- b. Teams or groups from any school, college, academy, and university can avail free and discounted services from any government agencies required for their developments.

ARTICLE V

PHILIPPINE SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE FOR AEROSPACE DEVELOPMENT

SECTION 16. *Establishment of the Philippine Special Economic Zone for Aerospace Development (PhilSEZAD).* – The ECOZONE shall be established at Davao City and Samal Island in the Province of Davao del Norte as indicated in Chapter I Section 5(g) of Republic Act No. 7916 or “The Special Economic Zone Act of 1995.”

SECTION 17. *Criteria for the Establishment of PhilSEZAD.* – Detailed feasibility that includes an engineering perspective must conform to the following criteria:

- a. The proposed area has established roads, internet connectivity, telephone lines, ports, airports, and has a capability to undergo developments;
- b. The availability of water source and stable electricity supply;
- c. The population shall be at least twenty kilometers away from any launch pad and test facilities;
- d. The availability of skilled, semi-skilled, and trainable non-skilled labor force;
- e. The area must be strategically located for the intended purpose of launches and tests;
- f. Financial centers such as banks are available; and
- g. The area must have an established customs control to eradicate possibilities of smuggling.

SECTION 18. *PhilSEZAD shall be Operated and Managed as a Decentralized Industrial, Trade, and Research Community with a Separate Customs Authority and Security.* – This ECOZONE shall be developed and managed in compliance to Chapter I Sections 7 to 10 and the remaining chapters of Republic Act No. 7916.

SECTION 19. *Governance of PhilSEZAD through NASLA.* The National Assembly for Spacecraft and Launcher Accreditation (NASLA) shall have the following functions and powers over PhilSEZAD:

- a. Set general policies on the conduct of operations within the PhilSEZAD as approved by the Philippine Economic Zone Authority (PEZA);
- b. Regulate individuals, academes, companies, and other concerned groups in maintaining utilities, services, and other forms of infrastructures within the PhilSEZAD;
- c. Submit an annual budget and financial report to PEZA;
- d. Propose necessary and timely development plans with at least twenty (20) years of justified usability;
- e. Exercise all the functions provided in this policy; and

- f. Render separate annual reports to the Vice President of the Republic of the Philippines and the Congress.

ARTICLE VI

NATIONAL GOVERNMENT AND OTHER ENTITIES

SECTION 20. *Relationship with the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines.* – The NASLA shall coordinate with the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP) for any flight and test related schedules that can affect the airspace safety and integrity of the territory of the Republic of the Philippines.

SECTION 21. *Relationship with the Philippine Space Agency.* – A comprehensive list of operators, developers, designers, and manufacturers of any sort related to spacecraft and launch vehicles should be submitted quarterly to the Philippine Space Agency (PhilSA).

SECTION 22. *Relationship with the Department of Trade and Industry.* - The NASLA shall ensure that individuals, groups, teams, academes, and companies are compliant to the Strategic Trade Management Act (STMA) of the Philippines with authorization from the Strategic Trade Management Office of the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI-STMO).

SECTION 24. *Relationship with the Department of National Defense.* – The NASLA shall submit a comprehensive list of registered spacecraft and launch vehicle developers to the Department of National Defense (DND) to enhance and maintain the national security interests of the Republic of the Philippines.

SECTION 25. *Relationship with the Local Government Units.* Except as herein provided, the local government units governing the PhilSEZAD and other development locations shall perform its basic mandates and authority in accordance to the Local Government Code of 1991 also known as Republic Act No. 7160.

Signed, submitted, and filed this 25th day of October 2022.

MR. DEXTER P. BANO JR., MBA – Candidate
Founder and President
Orbital Exploration Technologies, Inc.

Republic of the Philippines
Office of the President

Philippine Space Agency

OFFICE OF THE DIRECTOR GENERAL

8 November 2022

SENATOR RISA HONTIVEROS

Senate of the Philippines
Senate Office: Rm. 527 & 9 (New Wing 5/F)
GSIS Bldg., Financial Center, Diokno Blvd.,
Pasay City

Attn: : **Joana Marie Garcia**
Policy and Legislation Unit
Office of Senator Risa Hontiveros
Senate of the Philippines

Dear **Senator Hontiveros**:

This is in reference to the communication from your good Office dated 2 November 2022 providing the Philippine Space Agency (PhilSA) with a copy of proposed Spacecraft and Launch Vehicle Development Registration Policy by Orbital Exploration Technologies, Inc. (OrbitX) for the agency's reference and possible comment.

We would like to thank your Office for giving us notice of the said proposal. We find it timely and relevant in light of the global trend towards the commercialization and privatization of various outer space activities. Please be informed that we have earlier commenced internal work for our proposed policy or guidelines on spaceport and launch activities, and the proposal from OrbitX shall be a welcome contribution to this ongoing work.

We will get back to your good Office with our comments on the document. In addition, we kindly request that PhilSA be included as a participant in deliberations or discussion on this or similar matters. Succeeding communication regarding this subject may likewise be coursed through our Space Policy and Legal Affairs Division (SPLAD) under our Space Policy and International Cooperation Bureau (SPICB), with email addresses splad@philsa.gov.ph and spicb@philsa.gov.ph.

We hope you are keeping well and safe. Thank you very much.

Sincerely,

JOEL JOSEPH S. MARCIANO, JR. Ph.D
Director General

Ref. No. JSM-P2022-909

Office Address: University of the Philippines Diliman, Quezon City, Philippines
Telephone No: (+63) 2 771 9999
Email: odg@philsa.gov.ph

Website: www.philsa.gov.ph
Facebook: [Philippine Space Agency](https://www.facebook.com/PhilippineSpaceAgency)
Twitter: [Philippine Space Agency](https://twitter.com/PhilippineSpaceAgency)
LinkedIn: [Philippine Space Agency](https://www.linkedin.com/company/philippine-space-agency)